

PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS' (PSTs) KNOWLEDGE OF TEACHING AND TECHNOLOGY: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED ENRICHED SYLLABUS IN MATHEMATICS EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the integration of technology in Philippine teacher education. The study revealed the competence of PSTs' content, pedagogy, and technology knowledge integration. Findings showed a predominantly young female PST group with varying income and specialization levels. PSTs and cooperating teachers (CTs) perceive strong development across TPACK domains, particularly in technological knowledge. Significant influences from income and specialization on TPACK teaching competencies are noted, while age and gender show minimal impact. Discrepancies between PST self-assessments and CT ratings underscore the need for targeted curriculum enhancements. Mathematics PSTs rated themselves higher than their CTs, whereas English and Science PSTs were rated higher. Recommendations include revising admission policies, implementing professional development, and enriching curriculum content to address identified competency gaps and ensure robust preparation for technology-enhanced teaching practices.

Keywords: *Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs), TPACK Teaching Competencies, Educational Technology Integration, Mindoro Island Education, Syllabus Enrichment, and Mathematics Education*

INTRODUCTION

Integrating technology into education is essential for fostering accessibility and inclusivity, particularly in diverse contexts like the Philippines. By enhancing personalized learning experiences and facilitating blended learning approaches, technology empowers educators and students to thrive in the 21st century. This integration not only supports data-driven education but also fosters collaboration, communication, and the development of critical skills necessary for success in today's world (Vergel de Dios, 2016).

The Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) model serves as a crucial framework for understanding the integrated knowledge teachers need to effectively incorporate technology into their teaching practices. In the Philippine context, TPACK highlights the interconnectedness of content knowledge (CK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), and technology knowledge (TK), emphasizing their seamless integration to enhance learning outcomes. Studies indicate that many Filipino teachers feel unequipped to effectively utilize technology in their classrooms, underscoring the importance of frameworks like TPACK in guiding teacher standards and practices (Dublar, 2023).

The Philippine government has implemented national initiatives and policies to support technology integration in teacher education, aligning with the current shift to the MATATAG curriculum. The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) emphasizes technology integration as a core competency for educators (Department of Education [DepEd], 2017). This framework ensures that teachers can effectively incorporate technology into their teaching practices within the evolving educational landscape. Furthermore, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) has mandated through CMO No. 75, s. 2017, that ICT competencies and educational technologies be integrated into pre-service teacher education programs.

Despite these advancements, challenges remain in regions like Mindoro where access to technology is hindered by frequent blackouts and limited infrastructure. These interruptions significantly impact Pre-service Teachers' (PSTs) ability to consistently integrate technology into their teaching practices. Additionally, there is a pressing need for more studies to assess PSTs' proficiency in using technology for education in the region.

Moreover, PSTs in Mindoro express uncertainty about effectively utilizing available technologies due to limited resources and unreliable infrastructure. The geographical isolation of the island further exacerbates these challenges, restricting access to necessary support and resources for enhancing PSTs' technological readiness in education.

This study aims to investigate PSTs' knowledge of teaching and technology in Mindoro, which is essential for enhancing their capabilities in integrating technology into

education. The research aligns with the goals of the MATATAG curriculum and national education priorities that prioritize equipping teachers with modern pedagogical skills. Specifically, it seeks to profile PSTs concerning age, gender, monthly family income, and specialization; assess teaching competencies developed among PSTs regarding TPACK domains; and explore significant differences in TPACK competency development based on PST profiles.

By enriching TPACK syllabi, this study could significantly benefit PSTs by preparing them to meet the technological demands of today's educational landscape. Ensuring that PSTs can effectively engage students and improve learning outcomes through innovative teaching methods is crucial for the future of education in Mindoro and the Philippines as a whole. Stakeholders, including educators, policymakers, and community leaders—must collaborate to support initiatives that promote technology integration in education.

Research Questions

This study aimed to measure PSTs' TPACK teaching competencies as the basis for a proposed training program for developing teachers' TPACK teaching competencies. Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the PSTs in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Gender;
 - 1.3. Monthly family income, and
 - 1.4. Specialization?
2. What teaching competencies are developed by professors among PST-respondents in English, Mathematics, and Science subjects as rated by themselves, in terms of the following TPACK domains:
 - 2.1. Content Knowledge (CK);
 - 2.2. Technological Knowledge (TK);
 - 2.3. Pedagogical Knowledge (PK);
 - 2.4. Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK);
 - 2.5. Technological Content Knowledge (TCK); and
 - 2.6. Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)?
3. What teaching competencies are developed by professors among PST-respondents in English, Mathematics, and Science as rated by Cooperating Teachers in terms of the following TPACK domains:
 - 3.1. Content Knowledge (CK);
 - 3.2. Technological Knowledge (TK);
 - 3.3. Pedagogical Knowledge (PK);
 - 3.4. Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK);
 - 3.5. Technological Content Knowledge (TCK); and
 - 3.6. Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)?
4. Which domain in TPACK is highly rated by the following respondents:
 - 4.1. Pre-service teachers (PSTs); and

- 4.2. Cooperating teachers (CTs)?
5. Is there any significant difference in the development of TPACK teaching competencies among the Pre-service Teachers (PSTs) when grouped according to their profile?
 6. Is there a significant difference in the development of TPACK teaching competencies of the Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) as rated by Cooperating Teachers (CTs) and by themselves?
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METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research design to gather information about the profiles of pre-service teachers (PSTs) and the development of their Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) competencies by their professors. This approach is suitable for capturing a comprehensive overview of the participants' characteristics and competencies.

The population for this study consisted of PSTs from various State and Local Universities and Colleges on the island of Mindoro. A total of two hundred thirty (230) PSTs and [insert sample size] cooperating teachers (CTs) participated in the study, providing a representative sample of the educational landscape in the province

Data were collected using six (6) researcher-made survey questionnaires, which were divided into two parts: the first part gathered demographic information about the PSTs, including age, sex, family monthly income, and specialization/concentration; and the second assessed the development of TPACK competencies based on a standardized TPACK questionnaire by Schmidt et al. (2009-10), the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), and a compendium of syllabi from the Teacher Education Council. It included questions related to the PSTs' knowledge of technology, pedagogy, content, technological pedagogy, technological content, and pedagogical content. The questions were structured using a Likert scale of 1 – 5 to facilitate quantitative analysis.

Before administering the questionnaires, the researcher obtained clearance from the University's Ethics Committee to ensure the validity, content, and reliability of the results. This review confirmed that the research adhered to ethical guidelines, upholding the rights and welfare of the PSTs. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring their voluntary participation and the confidentiality of their responses. Upon receiving clearance from the Ethics Committee, the survey questionnaires were administered to the CTs and PSTs at their respective schools, with proper coordination with the School Heads. Formal letters of permission were secured to facilitate this process. Each participant was provided with instruments tailored to their field of specialization.

RESULTS

Profile of Pre-service Teachers

Age Distribution

The majority of the pre-service teacher-respondents were young, with 214 (93%) being below 25 years old and 16 (7%) falling within the 25-34 age bracket. This age distribution reflects a youthful cohort, which may influence their adaptability to technology integration in education.

Gender Representation

In terms of gender, 195 (85%) identified as female, 33 (14%) as male, and 2 (1%) identified as LGBTQIA++. This predominance of female respondents is consistent with trends in teacher education, where women often represent a larger percentage of the student population. The inclusion of LGBTQIA++ individuals highlights the importance of diversity and inclusivity in educational settings.

Monthly Family Income

Regarding family monthly income, 122 (53%) of the respondents earn less than PhP 10,000, while 70 (30%) fall within the PhP 10,000-20,000 bracket. Additionally, 34 (15%) preferred not to disclose their income, and 4 (2%) reported earning more than PhP 20,000. Understanding the income distribution is crucial, as it may impact access to resources and opportunities for these pre-service teachers.

Specialization

In terms of academic specialization, 104 (45%) of the PSTs specialize in English, 64 (28%) in Science, and 62 (27%) in Mathematics. This distribution indicates a strong emphasis on language and literacy, which may influence the pedagogical approaches adopted by the PSTs in their future classrooms.

The demographic profile of the pre-service teachers reveals a predominantly young, female cohort with varying income levels and specializations. These characteristics are essential for understanding the context in which TPACK competencies are developed and integrated into their teacher education programs.

Teaching competencies developed among Pre-service Teachers in English, Mathematics, and Science as rated by Pre-service Teachers themselves

Table 1. Summary of Ratings of the Teaching Competencies Developed among Pre-Service Teachers as rated by themselves

Specialization	Items					VERBAL INTERPRETATION
		25th Percentile	Median	75th Percentile	IQR	
English	CK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	PK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	TK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	PCK	4	4	4	0	Agree
	TCK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	TPK	3	4	4	1	Agree
Mathematics	CK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	PK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	TK	4	5	5	1	Strongly Agree
	PCK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	TCK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	TPK	4	4	5	1	Agree
Science	CK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	PK	3	4	5	2	Agree
	TK	4	5	5	1	Strongly Agree
	PCK	3	4	5	2	Agree
	TCK	3	4	4	1	Agree
	TPK	4	5	5	1	Strongly Agree

The data presented in Table 1 suggests that pre-service teachers (PSTs) generally demonstrate strong competencies in content knowledge (CK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), and technological knowledge (TK) across English, Mathematics, and Science. The consistency in ratings across most competencies, along with high median and 75th percentile ratings, indicates that PSTs perceive themselves as well-prepared and competent in these essential teaching competencies.

Teaching competencies developed among Pre-service Teachers in English, Mathematics, and Science as rated by Cooperating Teachers themselves

Table 2. Summary of Ratings of the Teaching Competencies Developed among Pre-Service Teachers as rated by Cooperating Teachers

Specialization	Items					VERBAL INTERPRETATION
		25th Percentile	Median	75th Percentile	IQR	
English	CK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	PK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	TK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	PCK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	TCK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	TPK	4	4	4	0	Agree
Mathematics	CK	3	4	4	1	Agree
	PK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	TK	3	4	5	2	Agree

	PCK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	TCK	4	4	4	0	Agree
	TPK	3	4	5	2	Agree
Science	CK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	PK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	TK	4	5	5	1	Strongly Agree
	PCK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	TCK	4	4	5	1	Agree
	TPK	4	4	5	1	Agree

The data presented in Table 2 suggests that pre-service teachers (PSTs) generally demonstrate strong competencies in content knowledge (CK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), and technological knowledge (TK) across English, Mathematics, and Science. The consistency in ratings across most competencies, along with high median and 75th percentile ratings, indicates that PSTs, as perceived by cooperating teachers (CTs), are well-prepared and competent in these essential teaching competencies.

The significant difference in the TPACK teaching competencies of Pre-service Teachers when they were grouped according to their profile

Table 3. Wilcoxon/Kruskal Wallis Test on TPACK Domains by Age Group

Domains	Age Group	Mdn	DF	Chi-square	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Content Knowledge	Below 25	4	1	1.27	0.2594	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	25 -34	4					
Pedagogical Knowledge	Below 25	4	1	0.31	0.5788	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	25 -34	4					
Technological Knowledge	Below 25	4	1	0.0463	0.8296	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	25 -34	4					
Pedagogical Content Knowledge	Below 25	4	1	0.0001	0.9917	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	25 -34	4					
Technological Content Knowledge	Below 25	4	1	0.0129	0.9096	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	25 -34	4					
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	Below 25	4	1	0.63	0.4292	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	25 -34	4					

At a 5% level of significance, the analysis revealed that all domains failed to reject the null hypothesis, as the p-values for content knowledge (CK: 0.2594), pedagogical knowledge (PK: 0.5788), technological knowledge (TK: 0.8296), pedagogical content knowledge (PCK: 0.9917), technological content knowledge (TCK: 0.9096), and technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK: 0.4292) were all greater than 0.05. This indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in the median ratings across these domains, suggesting that the development of TPACK competencies is consistent among pre-service teachers (PSTs) regardless of their age.

The significant difference in the TPACK teaching competencies as rated by PSTs and CTs

Table 4. Wilcoxon/Kruskal-Wallis Signed Rank Test on TPACK Domains by Type of Respondents

Domains	Type of Respondents	Sum of Ranks	DF	Chi-square	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Content Knowledge	PST	52,175	1	0.419	0.5174	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	CT	53,856					
Pedagogical Knowledge	PST	51,400	1	1.4678	0.2257	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	CT	54,630					
Technological Knowledge	PST	53,206	1	0.0209	0.885	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	CT	52,824					
Pedagogical Content Knowledge	PST	50,139	1	4.8675	0.0274*	Rejected Ho	Significant
	CT	55,892					
Technological Content Knowledge	PST	53,819	1	0.0219	0.8824	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	CT	52,212					
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	PST	53,541	1	0.1518	0.6968	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	CT	52,489					

At a 5% significance level, the results indicate a rejection of the null hypothesis for pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), as the p-value of 0.0274 is less than 0.05. This finding provides sufficient evidence that the median ratings on PCK from pre-service teachers (PSTs) and cooperating teachers (CTs) are statistically different. This discrepancy suggests that there are notable differences in how PSTs perceive their pedagogical content knowledge compared to the assessments made by CTs.

DISCUSSION

Teaching competencies developed among Pre-service Teachers in English, Mathematics, and Science as rated by Pre-service Teachers themselves

Among PSTs specializing in English, technological knowledge (TK) emerges as the highest-rated domain, with a median rating of 4 and a 75th percentile rating of 5. This indicates a robust foundation in integrating technology effectively into English teaching practices. Such high ratings suggest that PSTs are well-prepared to utilize technological tools and platforms to enhance language instruction, fostering interactive and engaging learning environments. The consistency in these ratings implies widespread agreement among PSTs regarding their proficiency in applying technological knowledge to support English education.

In Mathematics Education, technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK) stands out with a median and 75th percentile rating of 5. This signifies exceptional competence among PSTs in employing technology to enhance the teaching and learning of mathematical concepts. The high ratings in TPK indicate that PSTs are adept at integrating digital resources and tools to promote mathematical reasoning, problem-solving skills, and conceptual understanding. These findings suggest that PSTs possess

the skills needed to effectively leverage technology in Mathematics instruction, aligning with contemporary educational demands for enhanced digital literacy and innovative teaching methods.

Within Science education, technological knowledge (TK) emerges as the highest-rated area, with both a median rating and a 75th percentile rating of 5. This reflects outstanding proficiency among PSTs in utilizing technology to support Science instruction. The robust ratings in TK indicate that PSTs are well-equipped to integrate digital tools and resources to facilitate classroom scientific inquiry, experimentation, and data analysis. This competency suggests that PSTs can effectively harness technology to enhance hands-on learning experiences and promote scientific literacy among students.

The consistently high ratings across all subject areas align with the findings of Santos & Castro (2022), who highlighted the efficacy of targeted TPACK development programs in enhancing PSTs' confidence and competence in technology integration. This suggests that structured interventions can effectively align technology use with student needs. Additionally, Mercado & Ibarra (2019) provide insights into PSTs' self-efficacy in integrating ICT, linking perceived readiness with actual integration skills. This highlights the importance of aligning PSTs' perceptions with practical teaching outcomes.

The findings indicate that PSTs specializing in English, Mathematics, and Science demonstrate strong competencies in CK, PK, and TK. These competencies are crucial for effective teaching and align with contemporary educational standards, emphasizing the need for continued support and development in technology integration within teacher education programs.

Teaching competencies developed among Pre-service Teachers in English, Mathematics, and Science as rated by Cooperating Teachers themselves

In English education, technological knowledge (TK) emerges as the highest-rated domain, with both a median rating of 4 and a 75th percentile rating of 5. This reflects strong competence in integrating technology into language instruction. Such high ratings suggest that PSTs are adept at using digital tools to enhance teaching effectiveness and student engagement in English classrooms.

In Mathematics, technological knowledge (TK) also stands out, with a median rating of 4 and a 75th percentile rating of 5. This indicates proficiency in leveraging technology for mathematical instruction. The competence implied by these ratings suggests that PSTs can effectively utilize digital resources to promote mathematical understanding and problem-solving skills.

Similarly, in Science, technological knowledge (TK) receives the highest ratings, with both a median and a 75th percentile rating of 5. This indicates exceptional capability among PSTs in using technology to facilitate scientific inquiry and learning. The high

ratings in TK highlight the PSTs' readiness to integrate technology into their Science teaching practices effectively.

The consistently high ratings across TK in all three disciplines signify that PSTs possess the necessary skills to integrate technology meaningfully into their teaching practices, aligning with contemporary educational demands for digital literacy and innovative pedagogy. These findings are consistent with Muffidah (2019), who emphasized the importance of effective mentoring and thorough monitoring by CTs during the practicum, which is crucial in preparing PSTs to become qualified educators. This aligns with the high ratings PSTs received in technological knowledge (TK) across English, Mathematics, and Science, suggesting that effective mentoring enhances their competencies in integrating technology into teaching.

Furthermore, Boonsue (2021) highlights that teachers with high TPACK levels exhibit robust self-efficacy beliefs and actively participate in professional development activities. This is reflected in the high median and 75th percentile ratings for TK, indicating that PSTs possess solid technological skills and benefit from ongoing professional development and support from their CTs, which is crucial for effective technology integration.

The findings indicate that PSTs demonstrate strong competencies in CK, PK, and TK as rated by their cooperating teachers. These competencies are essential for effective teaching and align with contemporary educational standards, emphasizing the need for continued support and development in technology integration within teacher education programs.

The significant difference in the TPACK teaching competencies of Pre-service Teachers when they were grouped according to their profile

The uniformity in TPACK competencies across different age groups implies that the teacher education programs in place are effective in equipping PSTs with the necessary knowledge and skills to integrate technology into their teaching practices. This consistency suggests that the training and mentoring provided to PSTs are sufficiently robust to ensure that all participants achieve similar competency levels, irrespective of age. Factors contributing to this outcome may include standardized training methodologies and the supportive role of cooperating teachers (CTs), which help maintain high competency levels across the board.

These results align with the findings of Muffidah (2019), who emphasized the importance of comprehensive training and mentoring for PSTs, reinforcing the notion that age does not significantly impact competency levels. Boonsue (2021) supports this by noting that teachers with high TPACK levels benefit from extensive professional development and access to technology, which contributes to uniform skill development among PSTs. Additionally, Ocampo (2021) highlighted the significance of structured training and mentor support in Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs), further reinforcing the consistency observed in this study. Witt & Carraway (2017) and Ronfeldt et al. (2018)

also stressed the crucial role of CTs in providing guidance, feedback, and support, ensuring that all PSTs, regardless of age, achieve similar competency levels.

The findings indicate that the TPACK competencies of PSTs are not significantly influenced by age, suggesting that current teacher education programs are effectively preparing PSTs for the challenges of modern teaching. These insights highlight the importance of ongoing support and structured training in fostering the development of essential teaching competencies across diverse student populations.

The significant difference in the TPACK teaching competencies as rated by PSTs and CTs

Firstly, this finding highlights a gap between self-perception and external evaluation of pedagogical skills among PSTs. It appears that PSTs may overestimate their readiness or competence in integrating pedagogical strategies with content knowledge, while CTs provide a more critical assessment based on their experience and external perspective. This gap could hinder the professional growth of PSTs if not addressed.

Secondly, the variation in ratings may reflect differing understandings and expectations regarding pedagogical content knowledge between PSTs and CTs. This underscores the need for more transparent communication and alignment of expectations during the teacher preparation process, ensuring that PSTs are aware of the competencies they need to develop.

Moreover, these findings emphasize the importance of feedback and mentorship from CTs in developing pedagogical content knowledge. Effective mentorship can bridge the gap between self-assessment and external evaluation, helping PSTs gain a clearer understanding of their strengths and areas for improvement in pedagogical practices.

These results align with the findings of Mercado and Ibarra (2019), who emphasized the significance of TPACK self-efficacy and ICT integration skills among PSTs. Their research illustrates potential discrepancies in self-assessment versus external evaluation of pedagogical content knowledge, a theme echoed by Lobo et al. (2022), who underscore the role of internship programs in enhancing pedagogical practices through mentorship from CTs. Miranda (2019) further contributes to this discussion by examining the development of instructional strategies among PSTs, suggesting that differing perceptions may stem from varied educational backgrounds and mentoring experiences.

To address the identified discrepancies, it is recommended that teacher education programs implement structured feedback mechanisms that facilitate ongoing dialogue between PSTs and CTs. This could include regular check-ins, collaborative reflection sessions, and clear guidelines outlining expectations for pedagogical content knowledge. By fostering a more aligned understanding of competencies, both PSTs and CTs can work together to enhance teaching practices.

In summary, the findings indicate significant differences in the ratings of pedagogical content knowledge between PSTs and CTs, highlighting the need for improved alignment in self-assessment and external evaluation. Addressing these discrepancies is crucial for the effective preparation of PSTs and can lead to enhanced teaching practices in the classroom.

Conclusions

The study investigated the TPACK competencies of pre-service teachers (PSTs) in Mindoro, Philippines, as perceived by both PSTs and their cooperating teachers (CTs). The findings reveal that PSTs are predominantly young females with diverse incomes and academic specializations. Both PSTs and CTs perceive PSTs as having adequately developed teaching competencies across TPACK domains, with technological knowledge (TK) being the highest-rated area, indicating strong proficiency in integrating technology into teaching practices.

The study also found that monthly family income and specialization significantly influence the development of TPACK competencies among PSTs, while age and gender show no significant impact. Notably, the self-assessment of pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) by PSTs differs from the assessment provided by their CTs, highlighting a potential gap in self-perception versus external evaluation.

These findings have important implications for teacher education programs in the Philippines. They underscore the need to address discrepancies in self-assessment and external evaluation of PCK, potentially through enhanced feedback mechanisms and structured mentorship programs. Additionally, teacher education programs should consider the impact of socioeconomic factors and academic specializations on TPACK competencies, adapting their curricula and support systems accordingly.

Future research should explore the specific factors contributing to the observed differences in PCK ratings between PSTs and CTs, as well as investigate the long-term impact of TPACK competencies on teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes. Expanding the geographical scope of the study could also provide valuable insights into the generalizability of these findings across different regions in the Philippines.

Recommendations

In light of the findings, the following suggestions are presented below for consideration: Improve admission policies for poor yet deserving students in the Teacher Education Programs; Implement professional development programs to improve the teaching competencies rated lowest by the 25th Percentile of pre-service teachers-respondents and integrate these improvements into developing an enriched syllabus as an output; Prioritize strengthening teaching competencies identified as weak by the 25th Percentile of cooperating teacher-respondents by incorporating targeted strategies, activities, and assessments into the developed syllabus to ensure comprehensive

development among pre-service teachers; Revise and enrich the curriculum to include more content on Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK), Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK), and Technological Content Knowledge (TCK); Future studies will investigate the underlying factors contributing to significant differences in TPACK competencies based on monthly family income and specialization to develop targeted interventions for addressing these disparities; and To address discrepancies between pre-service teachers' self-assessments and cooperating teachers' ratings, Teacher Education Institutions should enhance Pedagogical Content Knowledge through workshops, practical teaching experiences, reflective practices, feedback and mentoring, and regular curriculum revision to align with current educational standards and identified needs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before involving Pre-service Teachers (PSTs) in the study, the researcher obtained informed consent by clearly explaining the study's purpose, activities, and potential risks or benefits, ensuring participants understood their rights to decline or withdraw without negative consequences. Participants were randomly selected without coercion, and their confidentiality was safeguarded by removing personal identifiers and securely storing data accessible only to authorized researchers. The study minimized potential risks, prioritizing PSTs' well-being and avoiding distress related to academic performance. It aimed to enhance PSTs' TPACK skills while transparently reporting methods, findings, and limitations to uphold research integrity. Throughout the process, the researcher treated participants with respect and consideration, valuing their educational experience.

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